

Zeolite as an Adsorbent for Thin Layer Chromatography Separation of some Carbohydrates and Catecholamines on Heulandite

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Heulandite, a naturally occurring zeolite, has been used as new adsorbent for thin layer chromatography. The migratory behaviour and separations of some carbohydrates have been studied. Separation studies have been repeated using scolecite, another zeolite and silica gel G as adsorbents for comparison purpose.

Zeolites have been used as adsorbent in chromatographic techniques. In this communication we report heulandite, a zeolite, as an adsorbent for thin layer chromatography.

Scolecite, a zeolite has been reported¹ as a new adsorbent for thin layer chromatography for the separation of some amines, triphenylmethane dyes, amino acids, carbohydrates, dicarboxylic acids and anions. Heulandite belongs to group seven and is a calcium-rich zeolite with a general formula $C_{12}Al_4Si_{11}O_{32} \cdot 11H_2O$ (It is available in Matwa plateau near Ujjain, Mohanpura, and at other places in India). Catechol amines have also been studied by ion-exchange chromatography on weakly acidic ion-exchanger with hydrophilic matrix². A reversed phase ion-partition system has also been described for catechol amine separation³. Hplc of free catechol amines in urine⁴ and determination of brain catechol-amines⁵ have been described. Ternary separation of catechol amines and carbohydrates using scolecite as an adsorbent has also been reported⁶.

We report herein heulandite (a zeolite) as an adsorbent for thin layer chromatography. The technique chosen on microplates, is a simple rapid method with better separation and this adsorbent does not require any binder as it sticks to the chromatoplates.

Results and Discussion

After studying the migratory behaviour of individual sugars on heulandite layer it is evident that maltose and lactose are characteristically retained and they do not leave the spotting point (giving R_f value nearly zero). Higher R_f values (Table 1) of rhamnose and mannose can be regarded due to *cis*-OH groups on C_2 and C_3 , which is not the case with the other monosaccharides used. Out of these two, the former has one OH group less than mannose hence it has higher R_f value. In case of arabinose the higher R_f value is due to its smaller size and lesser number of OH group. Comparatively lesser migration in case of galactose, glucose and fructose may be due to the reason that

in contrast to mannose and rhamnose, they have only one pair of *cis*-OH groups.

TABLE 1—MIGRATORY BEHAVIOUR OF CARBOHYDRATES

Compd.	R_f values		
	Heulandite	Silica gel G	Scolecite
Arabinose	0.80	0.74	0.76
Glucose	0.62	0.60	0.60
Mannose	0.76	0.66	0.70
Galactose	0.61	0.53	0.56
Fructose	0.65	0.62	0.68
Rhamnose	0.86	0.80	0.86
Sucrose	0.50 ^a	0.54	0.60 ^a
Lactose	0.00	0.00	0.00
Maltose	0.00	0.00	0.00

^aTailing.

Thus it is possible to separate lactose and maltose (which are non-migratory) from rest of the migratory sugars from their binary mixtures. Hence on the basis of this observation, the binary mixtures of maltose or lactose with other sugars were tried for separation. Clear separation of glucose, rhamnose, galactose, mannose, arabinose and fructose from lactose or maltose in their binary mixtures were observed. However sucrose can not be separated as it gives long tailings. So it was not considered for separation from other sugars. On the other hand, maltose and lactose can not be separated from each other as they are more or less of the non-migratory nature and are retained at the spotting point.

Thus it can be concluded that oligosaccharides are most difficult to get separated. Furthermore, because of their high molecular weight, they show lesser migration tendency and are limited to a small area on chromatoplates. In case of ternary separations, rhamnose with highest R_f value can be separated from comparatively less migrating galactose, glucose or fructose and totally non-migratory maltose or lactose.

From Table 2 it is clear that migratory compounds can be separated from non-migratory

or less migratory catecholamines in their binary (Table 3) and ternary (Table 4) mixtures.

Molecular sieving based on size of the molecule, increase of adsorption affinity due to functional groups in solutes, intramolecular hydrogen bonding or complexation with Ca^{II} ions in heulandite are considered to explain the differential migration of solutes.

TABLE 2—MIGRATORY BEHAVIOUR OF CATECHOLAMINES

Compd.	R_f values		
	Heulandite	Silica gel G	Scolecite
Adrenaline	0.80	0.80	0.88
Noradrenaline	0.62	0.78	0.62
Dopa	0.48	0.71	0.36
Dopamine	0.71	0.82	0.81
Tyrosine	0.00	0.75	0.00
Phenylalanine	0.82	0.82	0.78

TABLE 3—SEPARATION OF CATECHOLAMINES IN THEIR BINARY MIXTURE ON HEULANDITE PLATES

Sl. no.	Components of the mixture	R_f value*	
		I	II
1.	Tyrosine (I) + Adrenaline (II)	NM	0.80
2.	Tyrosine (I) + Noradrenaline (II)	NM	0.62
3.	Tyrosine (I) + Dopa (II)	NM	0.48
4.	Tyrosine (I) + Dopamine (II)	NM	0.72
5.	Tyrosine (I) + Phenylalanine (II)	NM	0.82
6.	Dopa (I) + Adrenaline (II)	0.48	0.80
7.	Dopa (I) + Noradrenaline (II)	NS	NS
8.	Dopa (I) + Dopamine (II)	NS	NS
9.	Dopa (I) + Tyrosine (II)	0.48	NM
10.	Dopa (I) + Phenylalanine (II)	0.49	0.82

*NM = No migration; NS = no separation due to overlapping

TABLE 4—TERNARY SEPARATION OF CATECHOLAMINES ON HEULANDITE COATED PLATE

Sl. no.	Components of the mixture	R_f values*		
		I	II	III
1.	Adrenaline (I) + Dopa (II) + Tyrosine (III)	0.80	0.48	NM
2.	Noradrenaline (I) + Dopa (II) + Tyrosine (III)	NF		NM
3.	Dopamine (I) + Dopa (II) + Tyrosine (III)	NF		NM
4.	Phenylalanine (I) + Dopa (II) + Tyrosine (III)	0.82	0.48	NM

*NM = No migration; NF = no further separation of migratory components I and II.

In the case of catecholamines, if we suppose that larger size of phenyl alanine may be the reason of its slower adsorption ($R_f=0.82$) and there seems no other factor for its retardation. Introduction of dihydroxyl groups in it may cause intramolecular hydrogen bonding or complexation with Ca^{II} ions present in heulandite. Any such process will inhibit the migration and hence the lesser migration of dopa ($R_f=0.48$) which may be due to these retarding factors. Decarboxylation of dopa gives dopamine with no COOH group hence the retarding factor in case of dopamine will be much weaker than that of dopa hence it will show more migration ($R_f=0.71$) than dopa ($R_f=0.48$). Now there is introduction of new OH group (in dopamine structure) in case of noradrenaline which may enhance the interaction between adsorbent and solute. The decrease in migration in noradrenaline ($R_f=0.63$) as compared to dopamine ($R_f=0.71$) may be due to this enhanced reaction. In adrenaline there is a methyl group more than noradrenaline, thus due to enhanced size there may be more migration ($R_f=0.80$) as compared to that of noradrenaline ($R_f=0.63$).

For comparison purpose, the work was repeated with silica gel G and scolecite using the same solvent system. Under identical experimental conditions it was found that in case of silica gel all compounds show nearly the same migratory behaviour, hence no separation was possible and the time of development was also more (20 min as compared to 12–15 min for heulandite). Thus under conditions studied heulandite proved better than silica gel G. However, scolecite shows equally good behaviour when compared with heulandite.

Experimental

The ir spectra obtained is similar to that reported earlier⁷. X-Ray diffraction data obtained also tallied with the data reported for the pure sample⁸. The chemical analysis for the sample used also coincided with the other reported samples⁹. Similarly optical and physical properties also tallied with the reported data for a heulandite sample^{8,10,11}.

After having characterised the sample, it was powdered and sieved through 45 μ sieve, then slurried in water (sorberent : water, 1 : 2), coated on micro-slides and activated at 110° for 1 h. Then the spot solutions of carbohydrates (1%, w/v in distilled water) and catecholamines (0.1%, w/v in distilled water with small amount of concentrated H_2SO_4) were spotted on chromatoplates. The migratory behaviour was studied in various solvents of eluotropic series. The solvent systems ethyl acetate-isopropanol (1 : 2, v/v) and dioxane-methanol-10% glacial acetic acid (4 : 0.5 : 0.3, v/v) were found suitable for separation of carbohydrates and catecholamines respectively by ascending tlc. R_f

values are given in Tables 1 to 2. The spots were detected by ninhydrine (0.25% solution in acetone) in case of carbohydrates and iodine vapour in case of catecholamines.

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